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EFFECT OF JOB ENRICHMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE**Dr. Ada Mac-Ozigbo & Dr. Cross Ogohi Daniel**

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3865384**Keywords:** Job Enrichment, Employee performance, Employee attitude and Motivation.**Abstract**

The main objective of this study is to analyze the effects of job enrichment on organizational performance. Non-teaching staff of University of Abuja, a public university in Federal Capital Territory (FCT) was the focus. Descriptive research method was adopted for the study using one hundred and ninety seven (197) valid questionnaires which were completed by selected members of staff of the university, in FCT, North-Central Nigeria. A simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study. The data collected were statistically analyzed in a significant manner. The result of the findings revealed that there are significant positive relationship between job depth, job training and core job dimension elements of the job enrichment and organizational performance while there was no correlation between motivators' elements and performance. Hence, increased recognition of task significance will stimulate the employees to further raise their commitment towards the attainment and realization of the goal and objectives of the institution/organization.

Introduction

The Job enrichment has become a basic tool for management to motivate their employee's in order to improve the performance and organizational growth. The main aim of job enrichment is to make the job more interesting, meaningful, challenging and responsible. Jobs are enriched to motivate employees by adding to their responsibilities with a greater need for skill varieties in their jobs.

Job enrichment is a way to motivate workers by giving them opportunity to use a range of their abilities; this is done by giving them more responsibilities and varieties in their job. The purpose of job enrichment is to reverse the negative effects of repetitive tasks requiring autonomy, and having effects such as boredom, lack of flexibility and employees dissatisfaction. An enriched job will contain a range of tasks and challenges of varying toughness, a complete unit of work and feedback, encouragement and communication mechanisms (Saleem, Shaheen, Saleem, 2012).

Due to the rapid change in environment and increasing level of competitive rivalry, organizations are now beginning to shift from the traditional ideological orientation of seeing money as the greatest motivating factor to a situation where workers today will continue to value their work, have more control in scheduling their work and deciding how best the work should be done and to be esteemed for the work they do (Saleem, Shaheen, Saleem, 2012). In job enrichment, workers derive pleasure and fulfillment in their position with a greater variety of skills and tasks that requires self- sufficiency

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This implies that employees can sense job dissatisfaction when they realized their jobs lack necessary challenge(s), lack adequate recognition, respect, creativity and other motivators, monotonous procedures, or a highly bureaucratic and over-controlled authority structure. Enriching job brings about internal work motivation

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and not just more work for them to do. Hence, Job enrichment serves as a roadmap to job fulfillment by improving the level of employees' responsibility, acknowledgement, creativity, autonomy and control of the job to be performed in the organization.

The principle of job enrichment in the practice of human resource management has tremendously been seen as a dynamic process of increasing the work structures and processes with an environment that gives room for autonomy, flexibility, personal growth and satisfaction to the workplace, (Aguinis, 2009). When tasks are routine, monotonous, repetitive and unrewarding with an over controlled authority structure, workers tend to be highly dissatisfied, bored and de-motivated. Job enrichment in organizational development has contributed in reducing these de-motivating factors by giving employees the right to decision making and control over their task in order to promote healthier. Though job enrichment doesn't work for everyone, the principle of individual differences indicate that some people tend to assume more responsibilities which later leads to skill varieties, self-sufficiency, personal growth and satisfaction while others resist. However, it can be reiterated that job enrichment becomes effective, meaningful and interesting to employees provided the tasks will increase job satisfaction and productivity.

Frederick Herzberg in the 1950s developed and saw job enrichment as 'vertical loading' of a job (Davoudi, 2013). This means that an enriched job should provide a range of tasks to be done with adequate feedback mechanism, encouragement and communication. A comprehensive understanding of "why" job enrichment is important for motivating workers to perform their tasks enthusiastically and relieve boredom will enable management in the public institutions to adopt strategic techniques that will help employees to focus more on job depth in order to gain more control over their duties.

To this end, the researcher undertook the study titled "Effects of job enrichment on organizational performance", with the public universities in FCT in focus to determine how organizational performance could be improved through job enrichment.

Statement of the problem

The problems of boredom and job dissatisfaction which consequently result in workers' low productivity, delay in administrative performance, work stress, psychological breakdown, absenteeism and lateness and eventually withdrawal of services are common decimal in most organizations. One possible reason for this development is that workers in these organizations view their jobs as dead ends and, therefore, have no pride in their work.

To prevent losing such valuable workforce to competitors as a result of boredom and job dissatisfaction, job enrichment could be an excellent means for recruitment and maintenance.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to assess the effect of job enrichment on organizational performance. Other specific objectives include:

- i. To analyze the relationship between job enrichment and employee performance
- ii. To analyze the effect of the relationship between job enrichment and employee attitude to change

Research hypotheses

The hypothesis is an informed guess or prediction that indicated what the researcher thought the result will be before the study was carried out. The following hypothesis would test correlation between these research questions and the study concerns in form Alternate Hypothesis. To establish the intensity of the relationship, the following hypotheses became relevant.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between job enrichment and employee performance

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between job enrichment and employee attitude to change

Research method

The present study was conducted using University of Abuja, the only public university in Federal Capital Territory (FCT); situated in Gwagwalada, North-Central, Nigeria. Descriptive research design was adopted. The questionnaire was randomly distributed to non-teaching staff in the Office of the Vice Chancellor, registry,

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bursary, physical planning, works and services, and those in the faculties, centers and other units of the chosen university.

Secondary data were obtained through books, journals, and internet. Empirical works of other scholars were consulted. A sample size of 197 was obtained from the population of 404 at 5% error tolerance and 95% degree of freedom using Yamane's statistical formula $197(100\%)$ of the questionnaires distributed $197(100\%)$ were returned. The questionnaire was designed in Likert scale format. The researchers conducted a pre-test on the questionnaire to ensure the validity of the instrument. Pearson moment product co-efficient were used to test the hypotheses

Literature review

6.1 Conceptual Framework on Job Enrichment

The concept of Job enrichment has become a fundamental tool for management in improving employees' motivation and organizational performance. It occurs when an employer through development and intensification, placed extra amount of work on employee(s) with the aim of making it more interesting, meaningful and, thus, increasing job challenge and responsibility. Jobs are enriched to motivate employees by adding to their responsibilities with a greater need for skill varieties in their jobs. Job enrichment is a job design technique that is useful in providing autonomy and encouraging employees' initiative towards high quality performance and job excellence. Mione (2004) sees Job enrichment as a managerial activity intended to provide employees with the necessary resourcing strategies to facilitate skill development opportunities. Job enrichment is increasing the volume of employees' autonomy, control, skill varieties and responsibility which invariably helps to reduce rigidity, tediousness, lack of creativity and employees dissatisfaction.

Job enrichment is seen as a process where management gives increasing responsibilities which are often assigned to the superiors to the employees. The essence of this is to help employees build the sense of self-management and self-sufficiency, (Neil, 2008). Williams, (2009); also posited that job enrichment is a fundamental aspect of stimulating the effort of employees by expanding job responsibilities and giving increased autonomy over the task processes and completion. Job enrichment is a systematic way of inspiring employees by giving them the opportunity to use a number of different types of skills and capabilities in performing a task. Job enrichment develops jobs vertically, and increases the variety of tasks in a job, (Robbins and Judge, 2011).

6.2 Factors that Predicted Job Enrichment

The following are factors that can predict job enrichment:

1) Core Job Dimension

The job itself is a predominant factor on job satisfaction. Jobs that are more involving, interesting, rewarding and challenging with optimistic features brings about higher level of job satisfaction. Several studies had also examined the relationship between the core job dimension and job satisfaction (Saavedra and Kwun, 2000). The elements of core job dimension which includes task identity, skill variety, task significance autonomy and feedback influences the performance and commitment of employees. These dimensions are considered below:

2) Job Depth

The job depth involves the variety of tasks in a job. It involves the planning, controlling and co-ordination of various activities in a particular task. Job depth is a means of outlining tasks and activities to be performed and assigning the tasks to employees within the organization. Armstrong, (2010) posited job depth facilitates how best to set schedules and plan work activities by understanding the job responsibilities, determining the suitable techniques for implementing the task and assessing the value of the work process.

3) Motivators

Herzberg's two factor theory provides a comprehensive analysis on factors that are associated with the job content (motivators) and job context (hygiene). He revealed that factors leading to job satisfaction are significantly different from those factors that bring about job dissatisfaction. The motivator factors are closely related to the feelings and attitudes of employees towards their job. Herzberg added that the motivator factors include the work itself, recognition, personal growth and advancement, a sense of responsibility and

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achievement. While the hygiene factors concentrate on the environment in which the job is performed. It also includes factors which include company policy and administration, working conditions, salary, and interpersonal relationship. However, these factors also expresses employees' feelings about the job but does not in any way contribute to motivation.

6.3 Job Enrichment and Employee Performance

In a capitalist economy as Nigeria's, it is difficult to adopt a job design practice to enhance employee performance. Invariably, enriched or enlarged job design alone cannot enhance employee performance. Therefore, organizations are usually influenced by the criteria of applying the most suitable job design characteristics (Okoh, 2005). At one extreme, marginal organizations enhance enlarged job designs in an attempt to create room for profit maximization. At the other extreme, some organizations adopt enriched job designs to enhance favorable work environment and to bring about improved organizational productivity. However, the concept of employee performance is most often dependent on the reward practices within the organizational system. Consequently, organizations are influenced by the criteria of ability to pay a prevailing reward structure in the industry (Okoh, 2005). At one end, some organizations pay the minimum wage fixed by government or what would enable them attract and retain the required number and type of labour. At the other end, some organizations pay well above the prevailing rate in the labour market because they want to attract and retain the very best and highest caliber of labour force obtainable. By paying higher rates, management is able to demand superior performance from its employees. The slogan „pay good wage, attract superior workers“ who can produce average and raise the profit margin of the organization is applicable here, such managers believe in the survival of the fittest as well as the economy of high wages to enhance optimal performance of the employees in an organization.

A sound reward practice is to base all wage practices on proper rates of evaluation of jobs in the organization. Job evaluation, according to Eze (2004), helps to establish fair reward differentials, internal consistency of wage rates, based on different job contents, for improved employee performance. For external consistency, it can achieve that by periodic wage survey of the labour market within its operational environment and industry.

6.4 Job Enrichment and Employee Motivation

In Lunenburg, (2011), investigation on stimulating employees by enriching jobs to make them interesting and challenging. It was noted job enrichment leads to higher job satisfaction and motivation. Employees performing enriched jobs usually experience lower absenteeism and turnover and high performance. And enriching certain elements of job alters people's psychological states in a way that develops their work success. Locke (1968) conducted research on a theory of task motivation and incentives and also in organizational behavior and human performance. The study observed that there is a positive relationship between participation and the completion of goals by the workers when their jobs are enriched. And that job enrichment also increase the motivation level and performance of employees in the work place and their tendency to achieve the goals also becomes more possible.

Fourman and Jones (2009) in their study found out that job enrichment influences motivation of employees who are in the middle of their career. Key factors described in job enrichment are hygiene and motivational factors. Their study aims to prove that apart from this vertical job enrichment adds more power, responsibility and knowledge to job thereby increasing motivational factors such as accountability, accomplishment, development and knowledge on the same job, therefore it leads to positive motivation and job satisfaction for the employee.

6.5 Job Enrichment and Organizational Performance

Studies revealed that when employees' jobs are enriched, job dissatisfaction and lower commitment tends to disappear. Organizational performance becomes vague the moment an employee feels displeased, disgruntled or discouraged about how things are done. Al-Nsour, (2012); examined the indispensable role job enrichment played on organizational performance. Part of these roles include: internal work motivation, greater commitment, employees retention, job satisfaction, distinctive and competitive advantage, improving work place opportunities which have significant and important effects on corporate success statistically. Cherati et al, (2013); added that the level of job enrichment goes a long way in determining how effective and committed a

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worker will contribute to organizational goal and objectives. Organizations who seek for greater performance and distinctive advantage must give better chances for employees' freedom, autonomy, control, skill varieties and responsibility, (Davoudi, (2013); which invariably helps to reduce rigidity, managerial monotony, lack of creativity, and employees' dissatisfaction. Employees' autonomy and control has often been seen as a strategic driving force to facilitate peaceful co-existence, affection, recognition, friendliness, freedom that are crucial for efficient performance capable of enhancing organizational effectiveness, (Lawal, 2005).

Test of hypotheses

Specifically, hypotheses one and two were tested using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between job enrichment and employee performance

H₁: There is significant relationship between job enrichment and employee performance

Table 7.1 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Job enrichment	2.8253	1.27682	197
employee's performance	3.1613	1.37593	197

Source: SPSS version 20.00

Table 7.2 Correlations

		job enrichment	Employee's performance
Job enrichment	Pearson Correlation	1	.716(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	304	230
Employee's performance	Pearson Correlation	.716(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	304	230

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS version 15.00

Table (7.1) shows the descriptive statistics of the job enrichment via, employee's performance with a mean response of 2.8253 and std. deviation of 1.27682 for job enrichment and a mean response of 3.1613 and std. deviation of 1.37593 for employee's performance and number of respondents (197). By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table (7.2) is the Pearson correlation coefficient for job enrichment and employee's performance. The correlation coefficient shows 0.716. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between job enrichment and employee's performance (r = .716). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .195 with 383 degrees of freedom (df. = n-2) at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r = .716, p< .05). However, since the computed r = .716, is greater than the table value of .195 we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that is significant relationship between job enrichment and employee performance (r =.716, P<.05).

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is significant relationship between job enrichment and employee attitude to change

H₁: There is significant relationship between job enrichment and employee attitude to change

Table 7.3 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
job enrichment	1.8261	1.16043	304
employee attitude to change	1.9065	1.26713	304

Table 7.4 Correlations

		Job enrichment	Employee's attitude to change
Job enrichment	Pearson Correlation	1	.955**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	197	197
Employee's attitude to change	Pearson Correlation	.955**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	197	197

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table (7.3) shows the descriptive statistics of the job enrichment via, employee's attitude to change with a mean response of 1.8261 and std. deviation of 1.16043 for job enrichment and a mean response of 1.9065 and std. deviation of 1.26713 for Employee's attitude to change. By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table (7.4) is the Pearson correlation coefficient for job enrichment and Employee's attitude to change. The correlation coefficient shows 0.955. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between job enrichment and Employee's attitude to change (r = .955). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .195 with 383 degrees of freedom (df. = n-2) at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r = .955, p< .05). However, since the computed r = .955, is greater than the table value of .195 we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that significant relationship between job enrichment and employee attitude to change(r = .955, P<.05).

Conclusion

This study supports the notion that the more opportunities for achievement in a job, the more satisfied the incumbents would be as majority of the respondents indicated satisfaction with their jobs as a result of the perceived adequacy of the opportunity for achievement. It could therefore be concluded that with increased opportunities for achievement, employees will be able to put into use those skills, knowledge and abilities acquired both on and off the job. Again, Job enrichment is an essential aspect in motivating employees for better and greater performance through a mutual sense for skill variety, task identity, task significance and autonomy.

Recommendations

From the research conducted, the following are the recommendations:

1. Since increased recognition of task significance stimulates the employees to further raise their commitment towards the attainment and realization of the goal and objectives of the institutions/organizations, management should therefore formulate and implement policies that will make employees to be commended for their efforts at executing tasks successfully as this may be a motivation and challenge to those who perform below expectations.

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2. It is recommended that since it was apparent from the review of existing literature and empirical results of this study that job enrichment is a vital instrument for organizations to equip their employees in today's dynamic world and highly competitive labour market, therefore human resource managers of University of Abuja should ensure that job enrichment design is properly implemented.
3. Human resource managers of the University of Abuja should take account of individual differences, attributes and people orientation to work. From the findings it was cleared that employees are motivated by different things, management should not generalize the motivation strategies, rather individual should be motivated accordingly, as what will motivate employee A may not motivate employee B.
4. The salary of employees should also be commensurate with their efforts so as to increase their morale and commitment. As it is popularly known that happy workers are most times the most productive workers.
5. Management should introduce more of job enrichment programmes such as vertical loading and quality management into the task structure of the non-teaching staff in the tertiary institutions. These programmes will give some discretion to the job holders to contribute to the setting of schedules and planning work activities.
6. Management should also embrace new ideas on possible new or alternative methods for completing tasks as well as creating opportunities for job holders to monitor the quality and rate of performance. Where individual job holder is held accountable for the success or failure of his/her performance, quality job would be stimulated and the overall organizational performance would increase.

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